

Synthesis of a new heterogeneous catalyst comprising 12-molybdophosphoric acid on to hydrous zirconia

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A new heterogeneous catalyst is synthesized by supporting 12-molybdophosphoric acid (PM) on to hydrous zirconium(IV) oxide (Z). There is an increase in the thermal stability of the material and the supported Keggin type structure does not get destructed up to 500°. Oxidation of cyclohexanol to cyclohexanone has been carried out to show that the catalyst is active.

Catalysis by heteropolyacids (HPAs) and related polyoxometalate compounds is a field of increasing importance¹. Though there are many advantages, the major disadvantages of HPAs as catalysts lie in their low thermal stability, low surface area and separation of catalyst from reaction mixture. Especially in molybdophosphoric acid (PM), the problem arises due to thermal decomposition and loss of active phase². The supporting of HPAs on suitable supports is expected to overcome this drawback. The hydrous oxides have multiphase applications. The surface hydroxyl groups of the hydrous oxides are responsible for the ion exchange behavior. Much of the work has been done on the ion exchange and sorption properties of hydrous oxides³ of group-IV since they are interesting from the viewpoint of their acid-base property. Not much work have been done on the catalytic aspects of the same. The ion exchange process can also be useful in catalyst development. It was therefore thought of interest to make use of the hydrous oxide as the catalyst carrier.

In the present work stress is given to the synthesis and characterization of a new heterogeneous catalyst comprising 12-molybdophosphoric acid (PM) on to hydrous zirconium(IV) oxide (Z). The new material (PM/Z) and Z have been characterized by chemical analysis, thermal and spectral data. A preliminary study on a oxidation reaction has been carried out to evaluate catalytic activity of the material.

Results and Discussion

The number of water molecules (n) was determined from TGA curves using Alberti-Torraca formula⁴. From the chemical analysis and thermogravimetric data, the formula for the Z may be proposed as $ZrO_2 \cdot 0.8H_2O$. The present materials show no change in colour or form on heating with

water. The materials are stable in different mineral acids like HCl, H_2SO_4 , HNO_3 , and bases like NaOH, Na_2CO_3 up to 4 M concentration.

The TGA of Z indicates about 10% weight-loss at 100–180° corresponding to the loss of absorbed/hydrogen bonded water molecules, after which a change in weight is reduced till 600°. The TGA of PM/Z shows 8% weight-loss at 100–180°. This may be explained by the interaction of PM with Z. The outer oxygen present in the heteropolyacid (PM) may interact with the H^+ of the hydrous zirconia to form strong intermolecular hydrogen bond. The intermolecular hydrogen bonded water molecules are strongly held and hence cannot be removed at lower temperature. This results in decrease in % weight-loss. It is known⁵ that PM gets decomposed at 350–375°. TGA of PM/Z shows no appreciable change in weight upto 600°, indicating an increase in the stability of PM.

The FTIR spectra of Z show broad band at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (asym and sym OH and aquo OH). The vibrations at ~ 1600 and $\sim 1410\text{ cm}^{-1}$ indicate the presence of H-O-H bending and Zr-O-H bending⁶, respectively. The presence of a weak bending band at $\sim 660\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to Zr-O bond. The Keggin structure⁷ has characteristic bands in the 600–1100 cm^{-1} region.

The main characteristic features of bulk $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$ are observed at 1062–1068 (P–O), 954–975 (MoO_4), 869–880 ($Mo-O_c-Mo$), 785–810 cm^{-1} ($Mo-O_c-M$)⁸. Here t tends for the terminal oxygen bonding to 1 Mo atom, c for the corner sharing oxygen connecting MO_3O_{13} units and e for the edge sharing oxygen connecting Mo's.

Sample dried at 100°: The FTIR spectra of PM/Z show bands at ~ 789 , ~ 858 , ~ 1066 and a weak shoulder at $\sim 963\text{ cm}^{-1}$ confirming the presence of the undegraded

$H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$ on the support. Further, there is disappearance of the bending band which appears at 1410 cm^{-1} in Z. It is known⁶ that when a hydrogen of the metal bound hydroxyl group, e.g. Zr-O-H in this case, gets involved in H-bonding the corresponding M-O-H bending shifts to lower energy region or it disappears. Thus the disappearance of the Zr-O-H bending indicates that there is H-bonding between Z and HPA, which is also indicated by TGA data.

Calcinated samples : For the samples calcinated up to 500° , there is slight shifting of $\sim 1066\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band but no modification in $\sim 789\text{ cm}^{-1}$ band. Also no band is observed at $\sim 755\text{ cm}^{-1}$ assigned to MoO_3 species⁹.

Electronic absorption spectra information about the non-reduced heteropolyanion¹⁰ due to ligand (oxygen) to metal (M) charge transfer¹¹. The electronic spectra of all PM/Z dried at 100° and with thermal treatment upto 500° were recorded. The spectra show λ_{max} at 250 nm, which is in good agreement with that reported earlier¹² suggesting the presence of the undegraded $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$ species. In other words, the Keggin phase remains unaltered up to 500° .

The surface area of Z is $84\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ and that of PM/Z is $78\text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. It is known¹³ that there may be decrease in surface area in case of supported catalyst in which oxides are used as supports. This is because of strong interaction with oxide support. A decrease in surface area of PW/Z is observed as compared to that of Z. This may also be due to a strong interaction of heteropolyacid with hydrous zirconia which is supported by TGA.

Oxidation study of cyclohexanol to cyclohexanone was carried out to evaluate the catalytic activity. Initial study was carried out with 100 mg of catalyst by varying the proportion of H_2O_2 . There was not much variation in catalytic activity with the varying concentration of H_2O_2 . Same reaction under same condition was carried out with the support (Z). The support was found totally inactive in the present reaction. For PM/Z, the % conversion of cyclohexanone was below 10%. When the amount of Mo supported on Z was considered 18 mg, the conversion was quite good.

The above studies show that there is an increase in the thermal stability of PM, and it keeps its Keggin-type structure when supported on to hydrous zirconium(IV) oxide and also the supported structure does not get destructed up to 500° .

Experimental

All chemicals used were of A.R. grade. $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40} \cdot nH_2O$ and $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ (Loba) were used as such. Cyclohexanol and liq. NH_3 (Sisco) were used.

The number of water molecule (n) was determined from TGA. The stability of all the material was checked in different acids and bases. The thermogravimetric analysis of the sample were performed on a Shimadzu DT30 thermal analyzer at a heating rate $10^\circ/\text{min}$. FTIR spectra (KBr) were obtained on a Bomem MB-104 spectrophotometer and electronic spectra on a Shimadzu PR 1 instrument using barium sulfate as a reference. Adsorption-desorption isotherms were recorded on a Carl-Erba sorptomatic series 1800 at -196° . From the adsorption-desorption isotherms, specific surface area was calculated using Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method.

Preparation of the support. Hydrous zirconium(IV) oxide (Z) : An aq. ammonia solution was added to a solution of $ZrOCl_2 \cdot 8H_2O$ (0.31 M) at pH 8.5. The resulting precipitates were aged at 100° over a water-bath for 1 h, then washed with conductivity water until free from chloride and dried at 100° for 10 h.

Preparation of the catalyst. $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40}$ supported on to hydrous zirconium(IV) oxide (PM/Z) : The support Z (1 g) soaked with an aq. solution (0.30 g in 30 ml) of $H_3PMo_{12}O_{40} \cdot nH_2O$. The resultant suspension was kept for 1.5 h at room temperature and dried at 100° with stirring for 8 h. Then PM/Z was calcined at 150, 200, 250, 300 and 500° in air for 4 h.

Oxidation reaction of cyclohexanol to cyclohexanone was carried out by refluxing a mixture of cyclohexanol (3 ml), H_2O_2 (30%; 3 ml) and the catalyst (100 mg) for 2 h. The reactions were carried out by varying the amount of the catalyst and concentration of H_2O_2 . The reaction product was analyzed on gas chromatograph.

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